

Jumpa Lahiri's Element of Diasporas in Interpreter of Maladies

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Abstract

In Indian writing in English, the novelists have quest many themes which manifested as in Diasporas, transnationalism, hybridity, cultural mongrelization, identity crisis enriches the Diaspora literature of the twenty-first century. Among the novelists, a few come from different parts of the country having the background of the diverse social, cultural and family and the use of English as their mode of expression exclusively in Jhumpa Lahiri's short stories highly favoured in sensitive confusions in the life of Indian immigrants' themes such as marriage problems, miscarriages and the disentanglement among the immigrants. Interpreter of Maladies is one among the collection of nine short stories. It is about the experiences of Indians' life in a foreign country and how they deeply flattened under the burden of alienation. The compilation attempts to be simultaneously both the collection of short stories and virtually a casebook on the relationship between the human kinds.

Keywords: Short stories, Indian Writing in English, Jhumpa Lahiri, Interpreter of Maladies, Indian Diaspora, relationship.

Introduction

Nilanjana Sudheshna Lahiri's born was in London on 11 July 1967, grew up in South Kingstown, Rhode Island. She was the daughter of the state of West Bengal of Indian immigrants. When she was in her second age, their family moved to the United States. Lahiri considers herself as an American. It is stated: "I wasn't born here, but I might as well have been." Lahiri finished her Doctor of Philosophy in rebirth studies. Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni and Jhumpa Lahiri as daughters of Calcuttans express the American and Indian relationship to their motherland, as well as their responses to immigration and assimilation. Jhumpa Lahiri expresses the complexities of the immigrant experience and marital snags in her short stories. It is highly focused through South Asian women. The concept of the Diaspora often identified in the present, and they deal with instantaneous social realities, her short stories also reflect her memories, or they negotiate the space between the homeland and

the diasporic setting. In the reminiscent and distressing instances of female oppression narrated in these stories, a transnational character is evident. Through this short story the plurality and specificity, lived moments and everyday practical reality captured and sometimes on synthesise of events, people, settings from the author's own life, with imagined characters and events.

Themes Adopted by Expatriate Writers

Jhumpa Lahiri undergoes the pain of homelessness, estrangement, and loss of belongings. Her struggling of being is between two ways of life, first leads to the feeling of depression and the other one frustration. In her short story, she expresses the thoughts of her own regarding her nation. The loss of homeland is the significance of consciously opting for a new home in a foreign like a missing child always thinking the motherland. The old recollections reflect in her works, and the new and unfriendly surrounding portrays the feeling of frustration and depression. It is a state of mind and emotion, which includes craving and longing for the homeland or the past. When a person leaves him and enters another, his old values come in a dilemma and the new one, in which he has adopted. Therefore the word 'Diaspora' is a location or dislocation from a geographical origin and relocation in another territory or country. The theme diaspora not says about the relocation but the inner feelings and sufferings. Several Indian English Writers recognized under such category of expatriate writers namely Salman Rushdie, Anita Desai, V.S.Naipaul, Rohinton Mistry, Abraham Varghese, Amitav Ghosh, Hanif Kureishi, Ved Mehta, Meera Syal, Bharati Mukherjee, Jhumpa Lahiri, etc.,

Sensitive Dilemmas Addressed by Jhumpa Lahiri

Jhumpa Lahiri addresses through her short stories dilemmas in the lives of Indians or Indian immigrants with themes such as marital difficulties, misunderstandings, and the disconnection among the immigrants. Like other expelled writers, she too suffers the same dilemma and undergoes the longing for Indian culture, which is a part of every Indian man and woman as an individual.

A Dominant Diaspora Writer

Lahiri acclaimed as a dominant Diaspora writer depicting the complexities of the immigrant experience in diaspora in her *Unaccustomed Earth*. This collection of stories is a well-thought-out, additionally to her composition of fiction writing. It won the coveted Frank O' Connor award of 35,000 thousand; this is one among the short story prize in the world. The stories were much-admired for depicting different aspects of the Bengali migrant occurrence. The collection of eight stories revolves around the quest for identity in relationships. In February 2010 Jhumpa Lahiri appointed as a member of the Committee on the Arts and Humanities one along with five members. Her novel *The Lowland* was placed on the shortlist for the Man Booker Prize in September 2013. This was also long-listed for the National Book award for fiction in October 2013.

Real Experiences

Themes Jhumpa Lahiri's as alienation and assimilation, love and marriage, home, exile, self-identity, or grasp the essence and experiences of her. Her real experiences take the readers to journey into the new world of a foreign land. Her story theme makes the readers be aware of displacement by emphasizing the pain of exile. Undoubtedly Lahiri is the most commanding literary figure in English.

Contents of Interpreter of Maladies

Interpreter of Maladies is the short story about the experiences of Indians who live in alien country and how they deeply crushed under the burden of alienation. They presented in Lahiri's inter-continental journey during which she gets herself accustomed to both the cultures by her stay abroad and regular trips to India for every summer. Her emotion reflects through the western culture forms. Her writings scattered with the details of traditional Indian names, food, flavour, and wardrobe, which collectively give shape to her stories. Three of Lahiri's are set in India and employ the narrative voices and indigenous experiences of Indians living in India. She focuses on her short story regarding culture, each people are meeting and separating on their slight tensions and hushed moments of joyfulness or pain. Jumpha Lahiri pictures Indians' abroad of displacement, hold on to their native culture, attempt to put together themselves into their adopted homeland, and suffered tensions over moral and poignant issues.

The centre of attention of Interpreter of Maladies

Jhumpa Lahiri's Interpreter of Maladies concentrates on expatriation or immigrants of Indians whose have been on the move about from India to the United Kingdom and the United States or to a short visit to their native country, either confronting way of surprising, even perplexing, civilizing differences. Through Lahiris' experience of these continents, there are two East and West worlds have been brought, as in a simile, or even in a metaphysical conceit, which teases and please the reader. Whether they set in Bengal or Boston, these sublimely understated stories, spiced with humor and subtle detail, speak with universal eloquence to anyone who has ever felt the yearnings of exile or the emotional confusion of the outsider.

Narrative – Spatial rather than Sequential

Jhumpa Lahiri's narrative technique is to be spatial somewhat than chronological. Her style, structure, and characters are detached or impassionate which force the reader to see the verisimilitudeness object. Lahiri's narration gives world shuttles amid India and the United States. The excellent narrative techniques of Lahiri establish her as one of the towering figures in World Literature. Lahiri is in the necessity to narrate the pain in her works. She keeps on listening to the story of inconvenience, her parents encountered and her friends. She feels inner pain, alienation, and marginalization, a kind of bequest from her parents. Her most and prominent food and homeland are the most important elements of homesickness. Such a way the metaphors of food make their existence strongly felt in Lahiri's works.

Interpretation of Protagonists

Depiction Jumpha Lahiri's all heroes with their several senses of this world, Lahiri relates them with the likings for food. By writing this Diaspora work food as an image and have functioned in different aspects in literary works with women. Food may see as a cultural signifier in this short story. In the fast and globalized world Lahiri's positive and negative and complex ways, separation, resistance, assimilation and nostalgic longing are portrayed here. Domination, powerlessness, control, empowerment are depicted in her story.

Conclusion

Through Jumpha Lahiri's short stories deal Diaspora elements, multiculturalism, nostalgia, immigration, divergent of Indian Writing in English and relationship between sexes. Her concentration on narrative tends to be spatial rather than sequential, the depiction of protagonists, exploration of familial ties portrayed or depicted here.

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